

Serial Vision as a Character Forming Element of Visual Corridors Diponegoro Street Salatiga

Reivandy Christal Joenso

Department of Architecture, Faculty of Engineering, Musamus University

ABSTRACT: Diponegoro Street is one of the main roads in Salatiga City, where there are still many buildings from the Dutch Colonial and vegetation in the form of large trees which visually gives its own characteristics and can describe Salatiga City as a resting place in the past. Over time, the Diponegoro road underwent a physical change in line with urban needs. It is feared that there will be a shift in the visual character so that this study aims to determine the visual character of the corridor which can be done through serial vision analysis. The method used is a descriptive exploratory approach where the researcher acts as the main instrument in digging and analyzing field data. The results show that the character of the Diponegoro Street corridor as a heritage area of the Dutch Colonial is getting stronger towards the east which is marked by the dominance of the Dutch Colonial buildings, vegetation in the form of large trees, and elements on street furniture with classical designs.

KEYWORDS: Serial Vision, Visual Character, Diponegoro Street Salatiga

1. INTRODUCTION

The city of Salatiga is a city that already existed during the reign of the Dutch Colonial, which is popular and is well known for its beauty because it is supported by geographical factors, fresh air and a very strategic location so that it is used as an area for resting. One of the roads that can describe these conditions is Diponegoro Street which is one of the main roads in Salatiga City. There are many Dutch colonial heritage buildings and vegetation in the form of large trees on Diponegoro Street Salatiga which visually gives its own characteristics and can describe Salatiga City as a resting place in the past.

In its development, Diponegoro Street underwent changes in line with urban needs which resulted in changes in the physical formation of buildings with typical Dutch Colonial architecture into modern architecture. It is feared that there will be a shift in the visual character that has an impact on changing the image of Diponegoro Street, Salatiga City.

Hartanti (2014) states that in the process of someone seeing, feeling and absorbing the information presented in a road corridor, it will shape the perception of the road environment. This can provide an understanding that the road is an element of the city that plays a very important role in shaping the character and identity of the city. In addition, Lynch (1960) in his theory of city imagery also states that roads as track elements are the most dominant elements in forming the image of a city because through roads people can recognize

other city image elements, namely landmarks, nodes, edges and districts.

Cullen (1961) states that the visual character of an area that has attractiveness is a character with dynamic formal characteristics and can be captured through a holistic view in the form of a continuous or serial observation that has a visual unit with continuous diversity in an integrated manner and forms a pattern. special. This serial vision is obtained through the movement of observers from one place to another in a regional corridor.

Therefore, in an effort to maintain the characteristics of the Diponegoro Street Salatiga as a corridor from the Dutch Colonial heritage, it is necessary to study the visual character of the Diponegoro Street Salatiga which can be done through serial vision analysis.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Corridor Visual Character

Visual can be interpreted as vision. Sight is the ability of the eye to perceive or recognize an invisible being and interpret it. According to Cullen (1961), visuals are related to the view of an object and the surrounding environment seen by an observer. Smardon, (1986) states that a visual sign has a certain quality based on the main characteristics that can be physically seen and can provide attributes to visual sources in a visual system.

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Corridor can be interpreted as a road or path. According to Krier (2001), broadly speaking, a corridor has a meaning, namely as a road that functions as a liaison between areas that are bounded and formed by two rows of barriers in the form of buildings and trees on the right and left and then form a space. In addition, Lynch (1960) states that roads as elements of movement trajectories or paths are the most dominant elements in shaping the image of the city because through roads people can recognize other city image elements, namely landmarks, nodes, edges and districts.

It can be concluded that the visual character of the corridor is a main characteristic that can be seen or the appearance of a street space with a long shape that functions as a liaison between two areas which consists of two rows of building masses, trees, and road furniture on the left and right sides of the street space. where this main characteristic can represent the area and also be a differentiator of the area with other areas. Identification of the visual character of the corridor can be done by observing a series of physical elements and the feeling of space formed from the physical form of the elements that form the visual character of the area.

2.2 Serial Vision

Cullen (1961) argues that the serial vision system is a psychological phenomenon related to physical appearance that can cause certain emotions. The physical appearance is related to the arrangement and arrangement of the environment as well as the visual correlation which is divided into two parts, namely related to place and content. Place is related to a reaction or feeling of the observer when he is in a certain environment when he sees the relationship between places and the continuity between places. Place has to do with possession, possession in movement, and focal point. Content relates to the structure of the corridor elements, in the form of content or content contained in a corridor. Matters related to content are Incident, Intricacy, Intimacy, Occupied Territory, and Foils.

3. RESEARCH METHODS

This research was conducted using a descriptive exploratory approach with the aim of finding previously unknown problems. Sukmadinata (2006) explains that descriptive research is a form of research aimed at describing existing phenomena, both natural phenomena and man-made phenomena. The phenomena can be in the form of forms, activities, characteristics, changes, relationships, similarities, and differences between one phenomenon and another. In this study, the researcher acts as the main instrument that plays a role in digging up field data without using respondents. Furthermore, in the analysis stage, the data in the field will be analyzed using related theories.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The research location is on Diponegoro Street Salatiga which is the main route connecting Semarang City and Solo City. Diponegoro Street is a two-way street that is traversed by various private vehicles and public transportation, both inter-provincial transportation, inter-city transportation, and transportation within the city so that it has a high traffic density.

Figure 1. Research Location

The pattern of traffic movement on Diponegoro Street is a two-way movement, so in this discussion the serial vision analysis process will be carried out with the observer's movement in two directions, namely from west to east and from east to west. The serial vision analysis process is carried out by determining the position of the observations and taking pictures directly of the conditions in the field in order to get the actual conditions in the field by considering the visual elements contained in the Diponegoro Street Salatiga.

4.1 Serial vision from the West to the East

Observations were made through 10 observation points with relatively equal distances between observation points and were carried out sequentially from west to east.

1. Observation Position A

Figure 2. Serial vision analysis at Observation Position A

In the observation position A, there are vertical elements with a combination of ornaments on the Roncalli Complex on the left (north) side of the Diponegoro Street corridor. Vegetation conditions that dominate visually and are relatively regular can be an identity for the building. In the color element, the left (north) and right (south) sides do not have a strong enough dominance because they appear to have cohesion through the similarity of colors between the buildings and their

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vegetation. When viewed from the height of the building, the left side (north) has a higher height than the right side (south). This is influenced by topographic conditions where the right side (south) is relatively lower.

2. Observation Position B

Figure 3. Serial vision analysis at Observation Position B

At the position of observation B, the diversity of colors begins to appear on the right (south) side where there is a combination of more than 1 color with an irregular pattern. While on the left side, it is still dominated by vegetation so that the visuals of the building are less exposed. The dominance of the basic shape at the observation position B is seen to be dominated by the basic shape of a square and gives a cohesive shape through similarities. At the height of the building, it is the same as the position of observation A, where the topography and vegetation conditions have an influence on the height of the side row of the corridor.

3. Observation Position C

Figure 4. Serial vision analysis at Observation Position C

At position C, there is an interesting visual for the color element. The existence of Ruko Shops No. 4 Segment 1 with a blue base color seems to dominate among other buildings which have white and green basic colors which are relatively integrated with vegetation. This will have an impact on the visual character of the Diponegoro Street corridor as a historic area, especially in the surrounding buildings which still have

the characteristics of the Dutch Colonial buildings, namely the Perhutani Office, Satya Artha, and the Oxford Course with a white base color.

4. Observation Position D

Figure 5. Serial vision analysis at Observation Position D

In the observation position D, the setback of the Military Police building affects the view so that only gates and fences are seen with black domination. The presence of black on the gate and fence looks very contrast with the surrounding buildings. In addition to having contrasting colors, the presence of ornaments and rhythm through the vertical elements on the gates and fences can be the identity of the building. In terms of building height, there is no visible contrast between the left (north) and right (south) sides. The existence of a Trade and Service Shophouse on the right (south) side with a height of >20 meters provides a balance of heights. In this observation position, seen from a distance there is a row of trees with a large scale in the road corridor.

5. Observation Position E

Figure 6. Serial vision analysis at Observation Position E

In the E observation position, the presence of Shophouse No. 13 Segment 1 North Side has contrast through color elements with a black base color because it is located between buildings that have relatively neutral colors. In this observation position, a row of large trees on the right (south) side of the road corridor can be seen clearly with a height that

dominates the surrounding buildings.

6. Observation Position F

Figure 7. Serial vision analysis at Observation Position F

At the observation position F, it is clear that there is a row of trees with a large scale that can give the character of the area. Another interesting thing is the dominance of elements in the pedestrian zone in the form of lighting, rows of garden landscapes, and benches that can provide visual quality from observers. With the dominating stereoscape elements, visual observations are limited to see the buildings, making it difficult to give an overview of the character of the building.

7. Observation Position G

Figure 8. Serial vision analysis at Observation Position G

In the observation position G, it can be seen that the STIE AMA building on the right (south) side is relatively dominant through the basic form elements because it has a much larger scale than the surrounding buildings. The existence of a row of trees is still quite visible and affects the height and visuals of the building. Rows of physical elements of the pedestrian path is enough to affect the visual observer.

8. Observation Position H

Figure 9. Serial vision analysis at Observation Position H

At the observation position H, the same as the two previous observation positions, the author has difficulty in providing an overview related to the character of the buildings at the observation position H. The dominance of rows of trees and elements of street furniture greatly affects the observer's visuals. However, if observed on a map, this observation point provides an overview of the St. Paul's church building which is a building that has a dominant scale of basic forms, ornaments, vertical elements, and openings that allow an observer to gain a greater sense of place because of the identity they have. In its existing condition, this cannot be obtained because the dominance of vegetation is strong enough to affect the face of this building.

9. Observation Position I

Figure 10. Serial vision analysis at Observation Position I

In the observation position I, the observer's visuals seem to change because they feel out of the visual which is dominated by the rows of trees in the previous observation position. This observation position has a special visual in describing the visual character of Diponegoro Street as a historic area, especially in terms of buildings. This can be seen from the existence of Dutch Colonial buildings that are interconnected on the left (north) and right (south) sides, namely the BCA Bank and Hangiri Fusion buildings. This relationship can be seen through the roof and the shape of the

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building which is not found in other buildings. The singularity and contrast of forms in the two buildings can provide uniqueness to their environment. In addition, vegetation that does not dominate as in several previous observed positions makes these buildings have a strategic position because they are easier to see and reach.

10. Observation Position J

Figure 11. Serial vision analysis at Observation Position J

At the observation position J, the observation position leads to the Garuda Tamansari statue roundabout, which is the intersection with Jendral Sudirman Street, Patimura Street and Kalitaman Street where this observation point takes the observer out to a different characteristic from Diponegoro Street. This is because the area is a center of commercial activity so that the activity and physical characteristics of the building are relatively different from Diponegoro Street. In addition, the Garuda Tamansari Statue is a catch point in this observation position because it is located in the middle of a crossroads and is monumental so that it can strengthen the character of the Diponegoro Street corridor.

4.2 Serial vision from East to West

Observations were made through 10 observation points with relatively equal distances between observation points, carried out sequentially from east to west.

1. Observation Position A

Figure 12. Serial vision analysis at Observation Position A

At observation position A, you can see ornaments and vertical elements on the Mayor's Office Building with white domination on the left (south) and right (north) sides of the road. In some buildings, observers have difficulty in making observations because of the setback and vegetation on the face of the building. An interesting finding in this observation position is that although there is vegetation that quite affects the observer's position, the roof of the St Paul's Catholic Church is still visible at a distance of about 430 meters from the point of observation. The height of the building, the shape of the roof that has contrast and singularity makes this building stand out among other buildings even though the distance is relatively far. This gives the observer a strong sense of curiosity.

2. Observation Position B

Figure 13. Serial vision analysis at Observation Position B

At the observation position B, the observer is brought to an observation point where the St Paul's Catholic Church building is increasingly visible because of the singularity of the basic shape on the roof of the building and supported by the height of the building. In addition, there is a relationship between the left (south) and right (north) sides, namely through the similarity of the basic shape on the roof of the BCA Bank and Hangiri Fusion buildings. This is a picture of a strong identity from the Diponegoro Street as a historic area that has a typical Dutch Colonial building. In addition, the elements of the pedestrian path in the form of lighting lamps and benches are quite visually visible and tend to support the Dutch Colonial building because of its classic design.

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3. Observation Position C

Figure 14 Serial vision analysis at Observation Position C

At observation position C, we can see the appearance of the Church of Saint Paul which has been seen at observation positions A and B. The roof of the building which has a singular shape and stands out and is supported by the height of the building gives dominance over the surrounding buildings. If you look closely, this building has ornaments and vertical elements with a certain rhythm and repetition pattern so that it can become a stronger characteristic. In this observation position, some of these elements are less exposed due to the presence of vegetation in the form of a row of trees which is quite dominating the observer's visuals.

4. Observation Position D

Figure 15. Serial vision analysis at Observation Position D

At the observation position D, it is different from the previous observation position, where this observation position tends to be wider visually because it is a 4-way intersection where the road which is an open space provides a more visual picture of the landscape. While in other buildings, the author has difficulty in analyzing because of the presence of vegetation on the face of the building both on the left (south) and right (north) sides.

5. Observation Position E

Figure 16 Serial vision analysis at Observation Position E

In the E observation position, there is a building with a modern design on the right side of the corridor (north), namely the UKSW Economics and Business Faculty building with a height that is quite dominating among the surrounding buildings. This will visually have an impact on several surrounding buildings which are historic buildings, namely the UKSW No. 3 and 5 campus buildings on the right (north) and the Matutina Middle School on the left (south). The row of trees in this observational position is quite dominating, especially on the left side (south of the corridor) so that observers have difficulty in visually describing the building.

6. Observation Position F

Figure 17. Serial vision analysis at Observation Position F

At the observation position F, the dominance of the row of large trees begins to decrease so that observers can better provide a visual picture of the buildings. On the right side (north) there is an Al Azhar Islamic Elementary School building which has a dominant blue color. However, when viewed as a whole, the elements of dominance and color combinations between the buildings are relatively varied and irregular. Especially in trading shop buildings with more than 3 basic colors.

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7. Observation Position G

Figure 18. Serial vision analysis at Observation Position G

In the observation position G, you can see trade and service shop houses on the left (south) side of the corridor with a large enough scale so that they seem to dominate the surrounding buildings.

8. Observation Position H

Figure 19. Serial vision analysis at Observation Position H

At the observation position H, on the left and right there are historical buildings with Dutch colonial characteristics including the Perhutani Office, Oxford Course, and Satya Artha. These buildings have a relatively similar basic color combination, namely the basic white color. In addition, there is a Ruko No. 4 building on the right (north) side with a modern design with a blue base color that seems to dominate through the color elements. This will affect the visual character of the Diponegoro Street Salatiga corridor which is a historic area with the characteristics of the Dutch Colonial building.

9. Observation Position I

Figure 20. Serial vision analysis at the position of observation I

In the observation position I, the characters on the left (south) and right (north) sides are contrasting. Where the left side is dominated by buildings with a square base shape and a variety of colors with irregular patterns. While on the right side, it is dominated by vegetation in the Roncalli Complex and Pangundi Luhur Middle School. The visual of the building at Pangundi Luhur Junior High School is less exposed because it is blocked by vegetation and the setback of the building.

10. Observation Position J

Figure 21. Serial vision analysis at Observation Position J

At the observation position J, the vegetation dominance is still visible on the right side (north) with relatively less composition compared to the previous observation position.

5. CONCLUSION

The serial vision from west to east shows that the Diponegoro Street corridor has a visual character as an area of Dutch Colonial heritage that is getting stronger towards the east. This can be seen by the presence of a row of trees on the east side which is not found in the west side corridor. In addition, the presence of street furniture with the use of classic colors and designs can contribute to the formation of the visual character of the corridor as an area of Dutch colonial heritage. On the

facade of the building, it is the same as on the pedestrian path where the movement of the observation position from the west to the east further strengthens the visual character of the Diponegoro Street Corridor as a Dutch Colonial heritage area. This is indicated by the presence of buildings with styles that show typical Dutch colonial buildings which are more dominant than the west side. In addition, there are roof shapes on several buildings that appear to be related and can show the visual characteristics of the Dutch Colonial buildings in several observation positions, namely the BCA Bank and Hangiri Fusion buildings. This further strengthens the east side of the research location as a corridor with visual characters from the Dutch Colonial heritage.

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